

DEVELOPMENT OF LITERARY CRITICISM IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN 20TH CENTURY

Teacher of Asian international university

Karimova Go'zal Ixtiyorovna

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Abstract. *This master's thesis examines the specific aspects of the literary criticism in English literature (as an example of the works of J. Konrad). The similarities and differences of the criticism genre with other genres are analyzed. The essence, significance and novelty of the work are well explained. The topic of the dissertation is relevant, interesting and attracts the attention of the scientific community.*

Keywords: *criticism, literary genres, English literature.*

РАЗВИТИЕ ЛИТЕРАТУРНОЙ КРИТИКИ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ В XX ВЕКЕ

Аннотация. *В магистерской диссертации рассматриваются специфические аспекты литературной критики в английской литературе (на примере творчества Дж. Конрада). Анализируются сходства и различия жанра критики с другими жанрами. Хорошо объяснены суть, значение и новизна работы. Тема диссертации актуальна, интересна и привлекает внимание научной общественности.*

Ключевые слова: *критика, литературные жанры, английская литература.*

Research objects: Analysis of the genre of criticism in works and consideration of its features. Also, the aspects and characteristics of the criticism genre, its differences and similarities from other literary genres are studied.

Purpose of work: the purpose of this master's thesis is to study and analyze the genre of criticism, to compare it, to study and analyze the similarities and differences with other genres of literature.

Research methods: methods of analysis, description, comparison.

The results obtained and their novelty: The scientific novelty of the research is that the topic we have chosen has been studied by many researchers of the world to one degree or another, but their views have not been systematized and analyzed from a general point of view.

Practical significance: The practical importance of the research results is explained by the fact that they can be used in higher education institutions to conduct special courses for a more detailed understanding of the essence of the literary fantasy genre, as well as to create textbooks, training manuals and literature. guidelines in this area.

Field of application: This work is of practical importance for students of the faculty of foreign languages in studying the country's literature, in seminars and practical training. This is also of particular importance for literary scholars in the study of world literature.

I. Introduction

The newfangled world arises from the long slumbers of medieval ages with the world shaking slogans of equality, liberty and fraternity but humanity is still awaiting to realise these ideals. In the times when humanity is bleeding and haemorrhaging grotesquely with one poor child dying of hunger every ten seconds somewhere in the sad melancholy, a woman being raped every minute with inexpressible brutality, the heartbreaking crimes meted out to millions in the

outpouring insurgencies and unrest all around the world, some that will never even be known to humankind; it has become indisputably clear that the study of the humanities in general is no longer a luxury but a necessity, vital to our very survival as an enlightened civilization that we claim to be.

II. Main part

The articulate vision of moral, educational and political values of the world's multifarious cultures can't be understood today unless we don't revisit our past to understand where those values come from, the struggles in which they were forged, and the historical contexts which generated those struggles. In spite of succumbing to blind ignorance of nationalism, religiosity or chauvinism in all its manifold guises; it is now rather essentially important to undertake close, careful, critical reading of the Bible, Plato's Republic, Greek tragedy, Shakespeare, or Roman Law, Jewish or African-American history, likewise to examine the Quran and the long history of the Western world's fraught engagement with Islam. It entails not merely the call for critical and comprehensive reading of immediate text written in accordance with its language, style, rhetorical devices and deployment of literary techniques that confront us but also the need to understand that why and for what purpose the particular text was enacted or written. There is one discipline which is defined by its insistence on such strategies: this is the discipline of Art criticism, as operating through both practice and theory.

The word criticism has been derived from the greek word "Kritikos" which means "able to discern and judge. The most famous representatives of the fantasy genre are John Ronald Reuel Tolkien, Ursula Le Guin, Nick Perumov, Michael Moorcock, Roger Zelazny, Andre Norton, Andrzej Sapkowski, Sergey Lukyanenko and others.

III. Analysis

The newfangled world arises from the long slumbers of medieval ages with the world shaking slogans of equality, liberty and fraternity but humanity is still awaiting to realise these ideals. In the times when humanity is bleeding and haemorrhaging grotesquely with one poor child dying of hunger every ten seconds somewhere in the sad melancholy, a woman being raped every minute with inexpressible brutality, the heartbreaking crimes meted out to millions in the

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Criticism and creativity are inextricably mingled with each other. Despite its popularity, fantasy among the phenomena of the literary process of the 20th century remained on the periphery of researchers' attention for a long time. Meanwhile, the rapid development of fantasy in the literature of the twentieth century can be correlated with the fundamental changes that have taken place and are taking place in the spheres of social, scientific, informational, etc. Fantasy, as it were, responds to the changes in life - both with its content, reflecting the desire to return to the origins, to the mythical time, to the harmonious world, and by its artistic form. The fantasy genre is a notable phenomenon of the modern literary process, and its study is important both in literary and ideological terms.

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